

MEDICAL AND PHARMACEUTICAL ACTIVITIES AS OBJECTS OF LEGAL AND LAW PROTECTION

Rajabova Nodira

Pharmaceutical medical institute, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Recently, cases of problems related to the provision of safe and high-quality medical care have become more frequent. Experts note the fact of an increase in the number of offenses and crimes related to the medical and pharmaceutical field. Criminal cases are initiated against employees in these areas, and most of them are terminated at the stage of pre-trial investigation. The process of commercialization of insurance medicine is actively underway. Currently, private clinics account for 38% of the total number of medical institutions in Russia. Specialists in the field of medicine assess the future prospects for the development of paid clinics. With substantial investment in the opening of new medical facilities, the expansion of existing clinics, as well as in the process of joining small medical organizations to larger ones, there is a significant push to improve the provision of commercial medical services.*

Keywords: *medical, pharmaceutical, activity, objects, law-legal, protection.*

Relevance. This development is expected mainly in large cities. Unfortunately, this creates factors that influence the creation of favorable conditions for the manifestation of illegal behavior related to corruption. The fact that corruption offenses in the field of medicine are among the most common crimes allows us to conclude that it is necessary to study the field of medicine in more detail from the point of view of protection by criminal law. Another area of medicine that is prohibited, but rapidly developing and has a rich history, is treatment with folk remedies, without obtaining a license. The provision of such medical services is shady, but people believe that traditional folk remedies have been tested for years, forcing them to resort to just such help. Public health protection and its provision are among the highest priorities for state policy. Of course, in addition to a strong regulatory framework, practical decisions and the implementation of adopted regulations play an important role in the effectiveness and efficiency of policy actions.

The aim of the research is to analyze and study existing legislative acts in the field of regulation of medical and pharmaceutical activities, formulate recommendations for improving legislation based on the analysis conducted on the selected topic.

When writing the paper, the author had the following tasks: to study the current legal acts, to evaluate the results of scientific and technological progress, to identify the main problems that arise when justifying the issues under consideration in the field of law.

Materials and methods of research

The main methodological tasks are observation, comparison, analysis, and generalization.

The materials that guided the author of the study were the existing norms of the legislation of Uzbekistan, scientific and educational literature on the research topic, statistical data, as well as international regulatory legal acts.

Research results and discussion

The basic law of 29 August 29, 1996 No. 265-1-- " On the basics of public health protection in Uzbekistan" defines such a concept as "public health protection". The State is engaged in conducting health policy through the aggregate integration of certain measures. Such measures

have various aspects in their characteristics, namely medical, political, and economic. At the same time, the legislation assigns an important role to local self-government bodies, individual officials, and citizens, who in turn must properly perform their duties. These measures should lead to a reduction in the number of cases of morbidity due to various causes, the spread of these diseases among the population, promote and ensure the protection and preservation of people's health, and ensure the possibility of providing high-quality and timely medical care.

Basic principles of health protection:

- respecting the rights of citizens in the field of health protection and ensuring state guarantees related to these rights
- priority of the patient's interests in the provision of medical care
- priority of protecting children's health
- social protection of citizens in case of loss of health
- responsibility of public authorities and local self-government bodies, officials of organizations for ensuring the rights of citizens in the field of health protection
- availability and quality of medical care
- inadmissibility of refusal to provide medical care
- priority of prevention in the field of health protection
- compliance with medical confidentiality

All medical measures, examinations, and methods of traditional folk medicine are integral parts of medical activity. Also in this concept, specialists include the functioning and use of various types of medical care, for example, outpatient, resort, sanatorium. Medical activities also include specialized care, for example, in private clinics, as well as pre-medical care.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for liability for offenses in the field of medical or pharmaceutical activities. Our legislation requires licensing of certain types of activities. These include, first of all, those types of activities that, in their functioning, are capable of harming the rights and legitimate interests of a person and citizen established by law. A license is an official document that serves as a permit to engage in certain activities for a certain period of time, as well as when certain conditions are met. Here you can select the main and additional items. The main thing, of course, is relations that are aimed at ensuring the safety of citizens' health in the production, production and turnover of medicines and biologically active additives in general. An additional object is the order according to which you need to make a turnover of these funds. Falsifications of medicines, dietary supplements and other medical products, products of improper quality in the same field, as well as drugs, products and additives that have not passed state registration are the subject of a criminal act. To date, several draft laws have already been prepared, which see the main goal of protecting not only the rights of citizens-patients, but also the medical workers themselves. Considering this article, as an objective side, violations in the provision of medical services and the performance of their duties by doctors are highlighted, through non-compliance with certain conditions and standards that are mandatory in the medical field. These actions should lead to consequences that will be assessed as serious. It should not be overlooked that, in addition to providing medical and pharmaceutical services that are most closely related to the protection and maintenance of public health, a component of medical activity is medical activity for the transplantation of human organs or tissues. The science of breeding humans and improving the ancestral lineage is banned in France. The penalty under French criminal law is severe. Liability is expressed in a prison sentence of twenty years. This criminal law also provides

for a provision that punishes the removal or removal of any organ or tissue from a person without their consent. In France, the lawmaker also provided for liability for performing medical procedures that help to conceive a child without proper consent. Many experts in the field of jurisprudence note that France is an example that can be followed, and this, in their opinion, gives rise to a tendency to work in these areas of modernization of criminal legislation in the Russian Federation, in particular in the field of medical and pharmaceutical activities, public health protection. As part of a full-fledged analysis of the relevance of the topic chosen by the author, you should refer to examples from practice. So, a citizen was convicted for illegal practice of healing, treatment with folk remedies without obtaining the appropriate permission.

Conclusions. In conclusion, it is necessary to provide the formulated conclusions and recommendations that may have an impact on the improvement of legislation. To date, which are related to the field of medical and pharmaceutical activities, as well as encroachments on human life and health in the implementation of these types of activities, according to many experts, is inconvenient in practical work. Based on the experience of foreign countries, as well as when striving to achieve the goal of fair sentencing for crimes, ensuring the inevitability of criminal punishment for those who committed these offenses, such changes can lead to positive results. In our opinion, these norms in their sanctions currently do not correspond to a fair sentencing, since crimes in the medical and pharmaceutical spheres have a high degree of public danger, which is explained by an encroachment on the protection of human life and health. The analysis of legal problems in the field of committing crimes that infringe on the protection of human health and life, in the field of offenses in the implementation of medical and pharmaceutical activities confirms that the improvement of the state's criminal legislation is necessary and relevant.

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